

**Learning
Technology
Accelerator**

LEARNING TECHNOLOGY ACCELERATOR LEA

**D 5.3 LEARNTEH Accelerator Community System Scenarios and
Business Cases
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1. INTRODUCTION

In this deliverable there will be the definition of two scenarios and supporting business cases illustrating procurers' challenges within education and schools classrooms of the future (videos). Deliverable is included in the WP 5 Knowledge Transfer & Innovative Procurement Accelerator. The goal is to prepare the soil for future PCP and PPI processes, designing scenarios and business cases and transforming challenges into technical requirements.

Based on the roadmap and challenges and on the industry dialogues, business cases scenarios will be designed to support the preparation of tender documentation enabling the launch (in the future) of at least one PPI and one PCP call for tenders in the education and learning technology sector. Final versions of the business cases (D 5.3) will be displayed as **short videos**, spotting clearly the key messages for suppliers and other players, and will be made available at project website and procurers websites (and disseminated at large). Therefore this document is just supporting the videos.

Figure 1: LEA Business case video: PLEASE PPI

2. METHODOLOGY

A business case can be defined as a “justification for pursuing a course of action in an organizational context to meet stated organizational objectives or goals”. It is a rational practice to analyse and define investment’s real business value. Business case reasons why specific instrument should be taken. (Keen & Digrius, 2002.) The purpose of the business case is to justify the project but the reasoning can differ from one situation to another depending on the complexity of each. It defines the value of the undertaken project because the outcome of the project should be more than time and money invested in development phase. When describing a business case, the following aspects can be considered:

- **A strategic element:** describing the strategic need for the project.
- **Consideration of options:** what options were considered before this
- **Expected benefits and timescales:** what benefits will the organization receive once this project is complete and how long will these benefits take to achieve.
- **Costs:** what is the project estimated to cost and how will this be funded.
- **Return on Investment:** based on the expected benefits and costs, what is the expected return on investment.

LEA Learning Technology Accelerator business cases are build based on the results of WP 3 LEARNTECH Demand Policies Accelerator focusing on the challenges in the field of education faced by procurers and WP 4 LEARNTECH Dialogue Accelerator, focusing on industry analysis, challenge identification and dialogues with industry. Business cases are developed by JYU with strong support of EUPK and INOVA+. All the procurers have been involved with defining business cases scenarios, which will be the base of the future public procurement calls.

- one focusing in the IMAILE initial challenges and prototypes produced (Personalized Learning Environments, STEM, etc.) presenting drawbacks from previously research and the challenges for the future, which will support a future PPI procurement process;
- one focusing in additional Learntech challenge which supports future PCP procurement process. Each scenario will contain at least one complete business case, whit a vision, the ideal situation of the future classrooms and teaching

methodologies, potential strategies to reach that vision, technological/research problems or constraints that need to be overcome and its translation into technical requirements (that can feed awarding criteria for future procurement processes). However, it is possible that the complexity of a given scenario will require more than one business case. The business cases will represent the ambitions of the procurers' network for the future classrooms (and part of the LEA Roadmap 2030) considering the current known challenges and others still to identify. Final versions will be published online and disseminated at large inspiring other procurers and giving inputs to the market/suppliers. Final versions of the business cases (D5.3) will be displayed as short videos, spotting clearly the key messages for suppliers and other players, and will be made available at project website and procurers websites (and disseminated at large).

3. LEA BUSINESS CASES

One of the goals in WP 5 was to design the terms of reference for 2 innovation procurement processes based in innovative approaches. The project applications are presented here as business cases.

3.1 PPI "PLEASE"

Overall information

Estimated value: One million euro
Learning technology buyers group:
Finnish buyers group lead by Konnevesi municipality (FI)
Braga municipality (PT)
Citta di Torino (IT)

The procurement aims to purchase PLE:s innovative solutions & service for 6000 students corresponding to a purchase volume of one million euro (1 000 000 euro) that address the following **challenge:**

- The demand and need of **personalized learning** is increasing with an average scenario of one teacher per 23 students in the European classrooms. How can smart and intuitive personal learning technology **support teachers and students** to achieve **improved learning results** and at the same **save resources and time** for the municipalities?

For the envisioned upcoming PPI call for tenders the buyers group (Finnish buyers group lead by Konnevesi, Braga and Torino) will apply a coordinated approach where each procurer is responsible for carrying out a separate procurement for the innovative solutions it buys for its self. Hence the implementation of the PPI will be regulated under Finnish, Portuguese and Italian procurement law:

Finnish: <https://www.finlex.fi/en/laki/kaannokset/2016/en20161397.pdf>

Italian: <https://iclg.com/practice-areas/public-procurement-laws-and-regulations/italy>

Portugese: <https://gettingthedealthrough.com/area/33/jurisdiction/20/public-procurement-portugal/>

The OMC and preparations of the tender specifications are actions prepared jointly within the framework of the H2020 project of LEA

Scope of the envisioned PPI

The buyers group has the intention to buy the most innovatie PLE K12 systems on the market with the following functionalities:

- PLE must be easy to use and it must motivate and support students with their learning goals (save resources on teacher training and create a real impact on personal learning for municipalities)
 - PLE must save teachers time. (save resources and time for municipalities)
- PLE must be used everywhere and with every operating systems and devices. (enable learning to take place everywhere, and ensure interoperability with existing systems used by municipalities)
- PLE should early recognize school dropouts. (one early dropout can cost up to 1.5 million euro in tax money for a municipality in a lifetime)

Outperforming PLE functionalities

The innovative personal learning K12 systems to be procured must outperform existing solutions that are widely available on the market regarding the following **minimum technical functionalities**:

- Intuitive interface, which guides the user (no training needed to start using)
- Smart social, teamwork and notification tools for communication between key stakeholders and groups (teachers, students, parents)
- Basic learning analytics (measuring user behaviour in the system)
- Learning analytics dashboards for students, teachers, parents
- Motivational tools for students to set their own learning goals and support in reaching them (e.g. gamification)
- GDPR confirmed
- Compatible with interoperability standards, e.g. xAPI, LTI
- Mobile interface (compatible with BYOD)
- Interface & content in the local language(s)
- Seamless access to learning content from publishers which the teachers prefer

Additionally the buyers group looks for **additional innovative functionalities**:

- Detection of early school drop-outs (notifications on teachers, parents)

- Smart learning analytics (measuring learning - not only user behaviour)
- Machine learning/AI – smart system that adapts to the user (teacher, student) as well as learns from their mistakes and preferences and gives them guidance:
 - Recommendations of learning content to teacher while planning a lesson
 - Recommendations of additional personalized learning content for students when under/over performing from the class standard
 - Social recommendations facilitating peer/teamwork (teacher-teacher for lesson preparation & evaluation)
 - Social recommendations facilitating peer/teamwork (student-student to work together on their tasks)
 - Recommendations of learning content for parents to support their children’s learning
- Automated lesson planning and evaluation support for the teacher
- Gathering learning data beyond the system (e.g. from VR/IoT solutions)

Early indications of priorities per country

The education landscape in EU characterized by heterogeneity and diversity hence the priorities differ slightly from country to country. The following tables are results of the LEA need analysis workshops demonstrating priorities per procurer country. The full results can be found from D3.3. LEA Needs analysis: https://drive.google.com/uc?id=1_vhNTHMt6LyPonJAGwmhVICud2vW9SEN&export=download

FINLAND

MUST HAVE	Additional wish
PLE must be easy to use and it must motivate and support students with their learning goals. PLE must save teachers time.	PLE should support to work with transversal / future skills.

PORTUGAL

MUST HAVE	Additional wish
PLE must early recognize school dropouts PLE must be easy to use and it must motivate and support students with their learning goals	PLE should save teachers time and recognize school dropouts. PLE should be used everywhere and with every operating systems and devices.

ITALY

MUST HAVE	Additional wish
PLE must be ubiquitous and support the use of modern learning landscape PLE must support students to work together with transversal / future skills.	PLE should early recognize school dropouts. PLE should be easy to use and used everywhere

Deployment , operational phases and validation

Contract implementation will consist of a **deployment phase** (which is expected to be completed 9 months after contract award) and an **operational validation phase** of 4 months during which the solutions will be evaluated in real-life operational conditions).

The operational validation will be performed in collaboration with the contractors and the estimated approach:

- Local / national boards Each country assigns their evaluation panel with minimum requirements composed by an IT service expert, a pedagogical expert, teachers and students
- One Expert board supporting the procurers to guarantee a beyond user perspective in order to enlarge the market for the suppliers. The expert board is led by Jyväskylä University and the technical manager Kati Clements.

Possible sites and timeline for conformance testing prior to the PPI call: (?)

- Konnevesi, LEA school lab: Sep – Nov 2019
- Braga, LEA school lab: Oct – Dec 2019
- Torino, LEA school lab: Oct – Dec 2019

Envisioned PPI timetable

PPI timetable	Time-line	Months
Open tender period	Jan – Feb 2020	2M
Evaluation of bids and simultaneously offering of conformance test in school labs. One supplier per lot awarded.	March-June 2020	3 M
Decision note of awarded systems and signing contracts	July 2020	
Standstill period / preparations of installation by suppliers	July - August 2020	2M
Installation and deployment	Sep 2020 – March 2021	7M
Purchase	March – April 2021	

After sales support and evaluation, bugs fixing in schools	April – July 2021	4M
Total time PPI process	Jan 2020 – July 2021	18 M

IPR and market potential beyond this procurement

The selected operators will retain ownership of the **intellectual property rights (IPRs)** that they generate in the PPI and will be able to use them to exploit the full market potential of their innovative solutions *i.e. beyond this procurement*.

The market potential is estimated at 1 million euro beyond this procurement by strategic transfer of innovations to neighbouring municipalities within the procuring regions and to other educational procurers networks EU wide.

Information about European Union funds

This procurement preparation receives funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme, under grant agreement No 779803 (see www.learntechaccelerator.eu).

The EU has given a grant for this procurement, but is not participating as a contracting authority in the procurement preparations.

3.2 PCP "SEAMLESS"

H2020 PCP proposal in brief

- Project proposal submitted in EU funded H2020-call (**ICT-34-2018-2019**) with an overall budget of 6M€ (4,2M€ on PCP investment) in the education technology R&D sector.

This proposal includes nine partners from Portugal, Finland, Sweden, Italy, Belgium, Spain and Greece, including four procurers (Portugal, Spain, Finland and Greece) willing to support the learning of the future in European classrooms with a creative content supported by innovative technology.

Increased demand of teaching and learning **transversal skills** to better prepare the next generation of Europeans for future jobs and careers unknown today

Overall situation and challenge

Robotics, automation and AI will likely take over many future careers, hence European education should initiate to have focus on collaboration and creativity which are skills that are human related and difficult to replace by technology and machines (e.g. transversal skills)(Atenas & Havemann, 2015;). This will be one important path in order to prepare students better for future jobs and an international, dynamic and complex labour

market. How can teachers teach skills they were not on focus during their teacher training? UNESCO (2015) Defines transversal skills as “Critical and innovative thinking, inter-personal skills; intra-personal skills, and global citizenship”.

The policy paper: <https://www.aegee.org/policy-paper-the-importance-of-transversal-skills-and-competences-for-young-people-in-a-modern-europe/> recommends national governments and education and training institutions to cooperate on international and national level on the modernisation of education and training systems and on the recognition and validation of transversal skills and competences learned in formal, non-formal and informal education and training.

By using the PCP as tool to support this situation, we can challenge the market asking HOW innovative learning technology can support and measure at an early stage the teaching, recognition and validation of global transversal skills in traditional school curriculum as well as to assist teachers in this task.

Societal challenges

Prepare next generation European citizens for jobs and careers that don't exist today and an international, dynamic and complex labour market

Pedagogical challenges:

1. **Supporting teachers how to teach transversal skills** - Support for teachers to simplify recognition, validation and teaching of transversal skills in the existing curriculum (create a pilot case)
2. **Supporting students towards for increased learning of transversal skills** for future learning outcomes, careers and jobs (create a case)
3. **Supporting automatic measuring and recognising of learning transversal skills** preparing possible drop outs early to be better prepared in life (include a cost case of early drop outs)

Technical challenges demanding sustainability

- Reuse of digital devices in the classroom (no new digital devices shall be developed)
- SEAMLESS solution should work on the current LMS/PLE solutions within the classroom – Schools do not have a need for another platform, but a seamless experience with the current ones
- Rechargeable technology by kinetic energy produced during sport class and or recreation
- Seamless experience Innovative combination of Emerging technologies Blockchains AI

- Recognition of students learning transversal skills through informal channels (e.g. measuring learning through wearable devices, IoT etc.)
- Automated and self – instructive support (AI and measuring learning)
- Safe sharing of learning outcomes certificates, materials, tests and badges within European schools

Financial challenges

- Costs of dropouts. How could these decreases if potential drop outs will be able to manage new jobs and careers based upon transversal skills instead of traditional curricula measurements
- Decreasing the costs of training teachers
- Educating students to be flexible and skilled to adapt to the need of the labour market (decreasing so-called ‘Life drop-outs’ later in life)

Definition of transversal skills on several EC links

Transversal knowledge, skills and competences are relevant to a broad range of occupations and sectors. They are often referred to as *core skills*, *basic skills* or *soft skills*, the cornerstone for the personal development of a person (Larraz et al., 2017).

Transversal knowledge, skills and competences are the building blocks for the development of the "hard" skills and competences required to succeed on the labour market. https://ec.europa.eu/esco/portal/escopedia/Skill_reusability_level

Transversal skills, such as the ability to learn and take initiative, to work with others and solve problems, will help people deal with today's varied and unpredictable career paths. <https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=1214&langId=en>

As a measure against the changing context and their influence on the lives of young people, the European Parliament and Council set out a recommendation on the key competences for lifelong learning. In the recommendation they defined 8 key competences that are considered important for every European to develop and update throughout their lives to be able to adapt to change. They are based on the need for personal fulfilment and development, active citizenship, social inclusion and employment (9):

- Communication in mother tongue
- Communication in foreign languages
- Mathematical competence and basic competences in science and technology
- Digital competence
- Learning to learn
- Social and civic competences
- Sense of initiative and entrepreneurship
- Cultural awareness and expression

The recommendation encourages Member States to make it part of their lifelong learning strategies, and was reviewed in January 2018 (9). The key competences also function as the building blocks for further learning and career development (12).
<https://www.aegee.org/policy-paper-the-importance-of-transversal-skills-and-competences-for-young-people-in-a-modern-europe/>

Similar project funded by EC

<https://ec.europa.eu/epale/en/blog/developing-careers-through-transversal-competencies>

In the Needs Analysis performed to prepare for the SEAMLESS proposal, the theme of Youth Social Exclusion and Unemployment were brought up by the procurers both from the South of Europe as well as from the North. SEAMLESS procurers (Greece, Spain, Portugal and Finland) have all high Youth unemployment situation, which could be tackled e.g. with youth entrepreneurship (Transversal skills). See Figure 1.

Figure 1: Youth Unemployment in European member states 2019, Seasonally adjusted, source: Statista

SEAMLESS BUSINESS CASES	Return of investment (ROI)	Suggested measurement methodology
10% Decrease youth unemployment	Cost of youth unemployment 2016 Greece 5684.82 M € Spain 38356.58 M € Portugal 4099.04 M € Finland 5607.53 M €	Follow students progress after last year of secondary school, compare to average use of social benefits per country <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drop of months unemployed • Less welfare raised • Lower social costs
10% Decrease youth social exclusion	<p>Finland Case example: In Finland, one young person 'Dropped from the system' costs approximately 70 000eur / year</p> <p>Savings would bring 7 000eur/person (including taxes, social benefits, unemployment fee etc.)</p> <p>With 65 000 persons of age 15-24 unemployed, the savings for Finland potentially 455 000€/year with only 10% improvement</p> <p>One 'Life drop-out' costs approximately 1,2M € on their lifetime, which would make long term ROI rather high</p>	Interviews/survey of young persons with strong transversal skills

4. ADDITIONAL EUROPEAN COMMON NEED BUSINESS CASE IDEAS

Each scenario will contain at least one complete business case, whit a vision, the ideal situation of the future classrooms and teaching methodologies, potential strategies to reach that vision, technological/research problems or constrains that need to be overcome and its translation into technical requirements. Additional European common need scenarios will be gathered through LEA Project duration and published in LEA website: <https://www.learntechaccelerator.eu/>

Further promising topics and procurement challenges which the LEA procurers had interest in exploring included e.g.:

- Lack of qualified teachers in the classrooms (unequal distribution of teachers around the country areas/european countries)
- Support for Special Educational Needs (Dyslexia, ADHD, Autism & other)
- Connection of informal and formal learning
- Infrastructure issues (lack of networks, lack of computers)
- Appreciation of schools (by parents as well as students)
- Polarisation: Different schools have different budgets even in the same city or municipality área
- Teachers struggling for a regularization of their time of service
- Teachers working on multiple platforms and with many bureaucratic Jobs while doing their main teaching duty
- Students' mindfulness; supporting concentration (e.g. ready-made soundscapes)
- Teaching of foreign languages (Lack of native English and other language speaker teachers)
- Immigrants and their support when they do not speak the language
- School drop-outs
- Harmonising communication between educational stakeholders: schools, teachers, parents, students, principals, IT...
- Cypbersecurity of schools and specifically the effects of GDPR

5. Conclusion

LEA project designed through needs analysis activities further described in D3.3. two business cases for common European demand innovation procurements, one PPI and one PCP. One focusing in the IMAILE initial challenges and prototypes produced (Personalized Learning Environments, STEM, etc.) presenting drawbacks from previously research and the challenges for the future, which will support a future PPI procurement process; and one focusing in additional Learntech challenge

which supports future PCP procurement process. These business cases are presented in video format on LEA website. This document describes those business cases in more detail. Additionally, 14 new procurement ideas which the LEA procurers were interested in, were presented. These ideas can be turned into further business cases and they give an indication of the procurers' interest to buy solutions fitting those needs.

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